

Research Article

**THE ASSESSMENT OF USING
SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS IN
THE PROCESS OF TEACHING
ENGLISH IN HIGH SCHOOLS IN
GJILAN**

Linguistics

Keywords: supplementary materials, visualization, approaches, effectiveness, teaching process, methods and techniques.

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Abstract

Nowadays, English has acquired the status of an international language. It has become an integral part of modern culture, economics, politics, sport, education, art, tourism, science and other fields. It should be noted, that oral and written communication in English became a reality and a necessity: people often encounter TV broadcasting, simple instructions for use in English, as well as communication with foreigners, both in life and on the Internet. Mastering communicative competence in English, not being in the country of the language being studied, is a very difficult matter. Therefore, an important task of the teacher is to create real and imagined situations of communication in the classroom of a foreign language, using different methods and techniques of work (role-plays, discussions, creative projects, and others). Equally important is the task of involving pupils in the cultural values of the people - the native speaker. For these purposes, the use of authentic materials (drawings, texts, sound recordings, etc.) is of great importance. In this research, there were studied the innovative methods of teaching English language and supplementary materials, which are mostly used by teachers. By means of a questionnaire for both, teachers and pupils, it was possible to get to know which materials are mostly used at English classes and why, and also, to conclude why this or that supplementary material is effective or ineffective.

Introduction

Supplementary materials have a vital role in determining the effectiveness of the process of English teaching programs. Teachers are heavily reliant on a broad variety of materials to support instruction and students' learning (Thakur, 2015). In the process of utilizing such materials, experts have identified considerations of the realities and experiences of the first languages of learners, stimulation of positive interactions, motivation, provision of opportunities for integrated use of language, and flexibility as essential factors to focus on to enhance the effectiveness of language teaching Taylor & Parsons, 2011; PPRC, 2010).

Literature Review

Teaching ought to feature focus on the learners and instructors themselves as resources in the classroom, along with the context of the classroom. The use of specific supplementary materials ought to follow the identification of necessity during lessons. Effective use of the materials should involve provision of opportunities for learners' practical applications of language skills, in terms of speaking, writing, reading, creative tasks, group work, and listening. The offering of culturally relevant instruction approaches is vital in yielding quality in English instruction (Gaskaree, Mashhady, & Dousti, 2010).

Research Aims

This research aims to identify the approaches and considerations that are most effective in the application of supplementary materials to yield value and efficiency in the English language teaching process. It aims to establish, particularly, whether the application of context-specific, experiential, and individualized methods in consumption of English teaching materials is more effective than traditional and rigid methods.

The major objectives of this study

This study aims to contribute to the scope and field of knowledge about effective use of supplementary teaching materials in English language learning. In an increasingly globalized world, the English language has grown into one of the major mediums of communication at the international level, influencing a rising demand for effective English language learning, and hence effective use of teaching materials.

Research Questions

How can English language teachers assure the effective use of supplementary materials to yield high levels of efficiency in the acquisition of language by learners?

What specific approaches in the use of supplementary teaching materials have positive effects on the effectiveness of language acquisition among high school learners?

Research Design and Methodology

The study deployed a case study approach in which the researcher assessed the use of supplementary materials in the English language teaching process in three high schools, evaluating the level of success in their use. The research applied on three classes who learned English without supplementary materials and three others who learned English with them in the 12th grade classes at Natural Gymnasium “Xhavit Ahmeti,” in Gjilan, Social Linguistic Gymnasium “Zenel Hajdini,” in Gjilan, and Technical Secondary School “Mehmet Isai,” in Gjilan (six classes in total).

The research took place in a duration of ten weeks. The measuring instruments included a pre-test at the beginning of the research and a post-test for pupils at the end of it, and a questionnaire for teachers in order to evaluate the value of supplementary teaching materials in the abilities of students to consume lessons.

Data analysis of the results from the study involved computation of statistical values from the data, including means and variances, while also evaluating the results to identify important themes in the findings and assessed the impact of the materials on the teaching process (Anderson, 2010).

One essential limitation for the research concerns restrictions in the scope and field of study. The study's focused on only six classes from three secondary schools in Gjilan means that it was difficult to generalize its findings as sufficiently representative of population-wide trends.

Expected Results

Identification and use of teaching materials in ways that foster high school learners' incentives, choices, "ownership", creativity, and feelings of connection in the learning process represent the best methods of use of supplementary teaching materials to yield effectiveness in English language teaching (Williams & Williams, 2010).

Summary

Supplementary teaching materials should match the need for learning to be a social activity. Through application of supplementary instruction materials, especially in terms of assisting high and primary school learners to participate in teaching and learning processes, English teachers determine the levels of motivation and interest that students display in lessons (Kitao & Kitao, 1997). The application of supplementary teaching materials, including audio and tape recorders, presentations, visuals, and written texts, ought to place learners at the center of learning and instruction and prioritize adaptation to learners' needs (PEIDE, 2008).

Conclusion

In the use of supplementary teaching materials in English instruction, teachers ought to place high and primary school learners at the center of all strategies and methods. Contextual and individualized needs identified in the classroom should form the basis of selection and application of suitable materials for use in English instruction at the high and primary school levels (McCombs & Whisler, 2007; Leithwood et al, 2004).

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